

LIFE AND LEGACY OF MIRZO ULUGBEK

Scientific supervisor: **Rakhimova Zarina Uktamovna**

Akhrorov Alisherkhuja

2nd year student of Asia International University

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Abstract. *Mirzo Ulugbek (1394-1449) was descendant of Great ruler and emperor Amir Temur despite his royal duties Mirzo Ulugbek was also patron of mathematics and astronomy. Also he is founder of world wide well known historical observatory in Samarkand, Uzbekistan. His life and work inspired by many scientists and scholars till these days.*

Keywords: *Mirzo Ulugbek, Samarkand Observatory, Zīj-i Sultānī, Islamic Golden Age, Astronomy, Mathematics, Trigonometry, Spherical Geometry, Celestial Observations, Star Catalogs, Scientific Instruments, Cultural Heritage, , Nasir al-Din al-Tusi, Jamshīd al-Kāshī, Qadi Zada, Qushji, Islamic Science, Medieval Science, Historical Astronomy, Astronomical Tables, Legacy, Central Asia, Quadrant.*

Introduction.

Mirzo Ulugbek was Amir Temur's grandson, son of Shakhrukh. Also, he was a great astronomer and mathematician, significantly contributing to the scientific and cultural development of central Asia during the 15th century. Ulugbek's, especially in astronomy, efforts played a great role during a golden age of Islamic science. He established observatory in Samarkand, Uzbekistan, today known as the Ulugbeks Observatory. It was the place where he conducted extraordinary observations and calculations. The observatory was equipped with advanced instruments, and many skilled scientists were employed, which helped him to calculate and create precise astronomic tablets. One of the great examples is Zīj-i Sultānī. Apart from astronomy, Mirzo Ulugbek was also talented in mathematics, trigonometry and spherical geometry. Till this time, his contributions to astronomy, mathematics and in the other fields of science inspired and influenced many scholars , scientific and historical studies.

Main part.

In the 15th century brilliant mind and historical figure, Muhammad Taragay ibn Shahrukh ibn Temur Ulugbek Guragan was born in 1394 in the family of Shahrukh, the eldest son of Amir Temur. He is one of the great examples of Islamic world in terms of astronomy mathematics and role model for society. His birth place is Soltaniyah, Persia. From younger age he was tutored by renowned teachers and his passion for astronomy, law and science was undeniable, despite his royal status. However Ulugberk's mother disliked his interests in science wanted him to focus on politics more as a ruler. But his desire for knowledge was unremarkable and he became great astronomer, he wanted to explore the heavens, stars and the planets. He created instructions and kept the record of his works in his tables. Ulugbek became the ruler of Samarkand in 1409. When he became ruler of Samarkand he did not underestimated his duties and developed diplomatic relations with the yongle emperor of ming dynasty. In 1416, Ming ambassadors Cheng Cheng and Lu An gifted silk and silver presents on the behalf of the Yongle emperor. Hence in 1419 Ulugbek sent his own envoys , Sultan Shah and Muhammad Bakhshi to china. One of the emissaries saw the the Yongle emperor riding a black gorese, which was presented by Ulugbek. In 1439 artists

painted the black horse with white feet and white forehead under the order of the Zheng tong emperor that was sent by Ulugbek. More than a half decade later, letter was sent to the Ulugbek by the Ming emperor regarding to show his gratitude for all the contributions from the Samarkand. Also he sent several golden vessels and jade, spear with a dragon's head, a high quality horse saddle and variegated gold embroidered silk presents and garments made for specifically Timurid prince's family. On the other hand he established observatory in Samarkand, today known as Ulugbek Observatory. Under his government city was vibrant learning environment for scholar to study. Because, the observatory was equipped with advanced instruments and full of knowledge, which attracted many scholars from all over the world. One of the great work of Mirzo Ulugbek is creation of Zīj-i Sultānī, a comprehensive astronomical table that surpassed any its kind and it was, too, ahead of its time. This historical tables not only preserves precise calculations of celestial bodies, including the positions of stars and planets but also contains detailed calculations of astronomical phenomena such as eclipses and planetary conjunctions Zīj-i Sultānī is based on extensive observations and calculations, and it remained a standard catalog for astronomers for decades. The observatory in Samarkand, with its unusual instruments and hardworking scholars, played a crucial role in the production of this groundbreaking work. Ulugbek's passion of learning and culture extended not only in astronomy. He founded several madrasas, one of the great example is Registan ensemble was build between 1417-1420 years. or Islamic schools, in Samarkand and other cities. These schools provided education in a wide range of subjects for its students, including Islamic law, theology, philosophy, and the sciences. As a result, madrasas attracted students from all over the world, making Samarkand a center of learning. His deep belief in the power of knowledge was crucial reason for his urge for knowledge. He understood the importance of preserving and sharing intellectual heritage of any kind of a knowledge in the Islamic world. Hence, these action promoted greatly for learning and teaching and preserved Timurid dynasty. However, despite his many establishments, Ulugbek's life was not without its difficulties. His great projects and his thirst for science was disliked by some of his family members and nobles. In 1449, he was assassinated by his own son, Abdul Latif. Ulugbek's death was the end of a golden era for Samarkand. However, his legacy lives on. The observatory he founded remains till today. The Zīj-i Sultānī nowadays, is still studied and acknowledged by many scholars. Also the madrasas he founded continue to educate students. Mirzo Ulugbek's contributions to astronomy, mathematics, and Islamic jurisprudence have a significant impact on the human history. His work represents exact point of Islamic achievements and his actions towards power of human mind and the passion of knowledge. Ulugbek's legacy is a reminder that even in times of conflict, humans can reach great heights. His story inspires us to understand the beauty and complexity of the universe, to seek knowledge. Precise observations of scholars and Ulugbek is amazing. Because, they we recorded without the help of any optical instruments, but by just naked eye. For example, tables presents coordinates 1,018 stars and the length of a year was determined by Ulugbek, 365 days, 6 hours 10 minutes 8 second, Later studies showed a difference of only 58 seconds.. That is why catalog did not lose its value until these days. More than 60 mathematicians and astronomers were invited by the observatory responsables. Jamshīd al-Kāshī was the first director of the observatory. After al-Kashi's death Qadi Zada led the observatory. After the death of Qadi Zada, Qushji was responsible for the observatory and he

was the final director. The design of Ulugh Beg's observatory in Samarkand was similar to a Maragha observatory, which was designed by Nasir al-din al-Tusi. It was 21 meters above the ground, with a cylindrical-shaped building with a diameter of 46 meters and a height of 30 to 33 meters and The building was made with brick. Ulugh Beg's observatory had the largest quadrant principle device. The building was tall enough for a maximal size of the arc of the circle. This device was placed with care, the arc, also, was scaled accurately This device was very flexible. It helped Ulugbek to observe the sun from the horizon, the altitude of a star and other planets. Unfortunately, after the death of Ulugbek observation was almost destroyed. In 1908 first document relating to the location of that place was established by Vyatkin. Unfortunately, most of the arc was destroyed leaving only part of sextant and basis of the building intact. However, Ulugbek's book *Zij-i Sultānī* and observation started to be recognized and learned by European scholars. By the 17th century, Ticho Brahe with the help of observations made in Samarkand was able to achieve precise equivalent and later, later on greater precision was achieved. Ulugbek's *Zij-i Sultānī* was welcomed not only in the East but also attracted the attention of European astronomers. The *Zij-i Sultānī* consists of four major sections. The first part, named chronology, illustrates several chronological methods. The second part is about practical astronomical issues, the third is serves as a movement of fixed stars related to the Earth's geocentric system, and the fourth part is dedicated to astrology, came from medieval astronomy which demonstrates fate of humanity. The astronomical tables measured by Ulugbek, which provide knowledge about ancient chronology, serve as a guide for astronomers and historians. Accuracy of Ptolemy's star map was confirmed by his tables, was presented in "Almagest. In 1648, in Oxford, England, for the first time the main work carried out at Ulugbek's observatory in Samarkand was published internationally. The project was prepared for publication and commented by by John Stevens, a professor of astronomy at Oxford University. After that, the celestial maps were published numerous times in England. Thomas Hyde after Seventeen years partially published a new edition of the famous observatory's in two language , Persian and Latin and titled it as a *Tabulae Long, as Lat he. Stellarum Fixarum, ex observatione Ulugh Beighi,*" in Oxford in 1665. As a result, the publication of Ulugbek's tables in Europe begin to attract significant amount of attention from all over the world. Because calculations was very time consuming and expansive at that time but the tables helped the scholars greatly and then was greatly appreciated. Twenty-five years after Hyde's Oxford publication, the catalogue from Ulugbek's tables were established in the pages of the "Prodromus Astronomiae" by the Polish astronomer Jan Heweliusz (1611-1687) published in Gdansk. In his work, Jan Heweliusz discysed the data from Ulugbek's tables with other resources all around the world. Ptolemy, Tycho Brahe, Riccioli, the Ottoman Prince Kaş, and Heweliusz is great example of this. In 1839, the French orientalist L.A. Sédillot (1808-1876) published Ulugbek's tables with the of title *Tables astronomiques d'Oloug Beg, commentees et publiees avec le texte en regard, I vol., 1st part, Paris, 1839.* Eventually, even more sophisticated analysis of Ulugbek's tables preserved in British libraries was published in the United States in 1917 by E. B. Knobel under the title *Ulugh Beg's Catalogue of Stars.* Which came from all Persian Manuscripts was aviable in Great Britain. It is outstanding and notable that numerous manuscripts of *Zij-i Sultānī* are preserved in European and Asiana stronomical and scientific journals and books.

Conclusion.

Mirzo Ulubek, one of the best generational minds of the 15 century made an outstanding contributions to the golden age Islamic science in terms of astronomy and mathematics. Also as a patron made several schools madrassas and created unique observatory in Samarkand which attracted many scholars and student worldwide. And as a ruler he bounded many diplomatic relations, comprehended law and politics greatly. His life and works was inspired many scientists, astronomer and mathematic not only in Asia but also in Europe. Many of his tables especially Zīj-i Sultānī helped scholars to understand and learn boundaries of galaxy. Till today, Madrassas and observatory he founded being used by European and Asian students and scholars till these days.

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